

Employee Engagement in Plantation Company

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Abstract— This study was to determine the employee engagement to employees of plantation company in PT X. This study involved 163 employees of the PT X plantation companies. The measuring instruments used in this study is Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) which was developed based on the theory of Schaufeli & Bakker (2003). The results show that most employees have a medium level of employee engagement. The meaning is, most employees are considered not too engaged to their company and can leave the company at any time when conditions are not favorable. The results of the study are expected to be an input for PT X plantation companies to enhance the social interaction and togetherness that exists in the director's office through activities such as gatherings.

Keywords— Employee engagement, company plantation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the most important aspects to produce achievement of organizational goals, for which organizations must implement various strategies in their efforts to maintain employees and maintain the quality of their human resources so that the organization can run dynamically (Margaretha & Saragih, 2013). In the past few years, the topic of work engagement or better known as employee engagement has become a concern for many industry players. Along with the increasing use of technology and the demands of efficient work processes, employee engagement is one of the most effective ways to increase productivity and improve business results. Employee engagement is a predictor of employee work outcomes, organizational success and financial performance (Harter et al, 2002).

Schaufeli (2013) states that employee engagement and work engagement are often equated to explain the concept of engagement, even though the two concepts are different things. Work engagement refers to employee relations with their work, while employee engagement refers to employee relations with their work and organization. Employee engagement is defined as a positive attitude, full of meaning and motivation characterized by vigor, dedication and absorption. Spirit (vigor) is characterized by high levels of energy and resilience to try and not give up in facing challenges when working. Dedication is characterized by feeling valuable, enthusiastic, inspiring, valuable and challenging. Absorption is characterized by full concentration on a task (Schaufeli & Baker, 2004). Kahn (1990) mentions that engagement is a multidimensional construct where engagement are not only emotional, but also physically and cognitively.

Schaufeli & Bakker (2004) suggest that employee engagement consists of 3 aspects, namely vigor, dedication and absorption. Vigor leads to high levels of energy and strong mental endurance when working, willingness to give more effort to his work, and persevere in facing various difficulties.

Then dedication leads to feelings that are full of meaning, enthusiastic and proud of work, have inspiration and are challenged with their work. Furthermore absorption leads to full and deep concentration, sinks with work where time feels faster and harder to separate from work, so it's easy to forget something around it.

According to Saks (2006) there are several factors that can influence employee engagement such as job characteristics, perceived organizational and supervisor support, and rewards and recognition. Job characteristics that are psychological meaningfulness can be obtained from the characteristics of work that is challenging, varied, requires various skills, is free to make their own decisions and opportunities to make important contributions. Then perceived organizational and supervisor support that refers to the employee's belief that the organization respects employee contributions and cares about their welfare. Then rewards and recognition are where employees will be more engaged to their work when they perceive a greater value of rewards and recognition for their job performance.

When employees are bound (engaged) with a company, employees have an awareness of the business. Awareness of the company's business is what makes employees will give their best ability to the company. Research shows that employees who are engaged (engaged employees) are more productive employees (Gallup, 2010). Employees who provide the best ability will have an impact on the company's performance. Saks (2006) states that many claim that employee engagement predicts employee outcomes, organizational success and financial performance.

Gallup (2004) groups three types of employees based on the level of employee engagement, namely engaged, not engaged and actively engaged. Engaged employees are builders, they always show high level performance. Then employees who are not engaged tend to focus on the task rather than achieving the goal of the job. They are always waiting for orders and tend to feel their contribution is ignored. Meanwhile the employees who are actively being staged are the cave dwellers who consistently show resistance to all aspects and only see the negative side on various occasions.

PT X is one of the plantation companies in Indonesia. The PT X journey began in 1906 with a small tobacco and coffee plantation near Medan, northern Sumatra. Starting from this small plantation, the Company developed into one of the leading agribusiness companies, having approximately 90,000 hectares of oil palm, rubber, tea and cocoa plantations embedded in the four largest islands in Indonesia, namely Sumatra, Java, Kalimantan and Sulawesi. PT X has a vision of becoming a leading agribusiness company that is sustainable in terms of plants, income, environment based on research and

development. The achievement of the company's vision today to become a leading agribusiness company, can not be separated from the use of labor to support the running of the company's business.

At its inception, the company diversified its plants into rubber, tea and cocoa. In the beginning of Indonesia's independence, PT X focused its efforts on rubber plants, which were later changed to oil palm in the 1980s. At the end of this decade, oil palm replaced rubber as the Company's main commodity. PT X has 37 core plantations and 14 plasma plantations. Farm management is carried out by applying research and development progress, expertise in the field of agro-management and skilled and professional workforce. The PT X business sector includes breeding, planting, harvesting, processing, processing and selling palm oil, rubber, cocoa and tea products. In the world of plantation industry, PT X is known as a producer of good quality palm and cocoa seedlings.

In maintaining the quality of its human resources, PT X always applies various strategies to its employees so that they can work optimally. According to Margaretha and Saragih (2013), if the organization does not maintain the quality of its human resources, it can cause problems in the organization such as a decrease in performance, dissatisfaction in work, burnout and a tendency to turnover. Based on data obtained from interviews with several informants, it is known that the turnover rate in PT X belongs to the low category, although in the 2017 - 2018 period there was an upward trend in employee turnover intentions but not as severe as in the company's acquisition period in 2007-2008. This turnover mainly occurs when there are employees at other plantation companies, both state-owned and private. Not a few employees who leave work to take part in selection in other companies, especially young and potential employees.

Based on the things described above, the researchers want to know and want to see the extent of employee engagement in the employees of plantation company at PT X.

II. OBJECTIVES AND METHODS

The method used in this research is a descriptive method because this research was conducted to see the employee engagement in the employees of plantation company at PT X. The population in this study were employees of the PT X plantation companies. The sampling method used in this study was accidental sampling. The number of subjects in this study was 163 employees. Data were collected using Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) which was developed based on the theory of Schaufeli & Bakker (2003). That scale has the results of the internal consistency reliability test with the Alpha Cronbach technique obtained a coefficient of 0.944. The result of the corrected item-total correlation value in that scale is > 0.30.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Overview score employee engagement of the PT X plantation companies can be obtained through the test significance of differences between hypothetical mean and the empirical mean of the score scale of employee engagement.

The following are hypothetical and empirical values which can be seen in Table I.

TABLE I. Overview of hypothetical and empirical value

Hypothetical				Empirical			
Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD
17	119	68	12.75	60	89	75.5	7.67

Based on Table I, the mean empirical employee engagement is 75.5 with a standard deviation of 7.67. While the hypothetical mean is 68 with a standard deviation of 12.75. Furthermore, based on the mean and standard deviation of the hypothetical, do the categorization of employee engagement as shown in Table II below:

TABLE II. Overview of the value of employee engagement

Range of Values	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
$X < 55.25$	Low	0	0 %
$55.25 \leq X \leq 80.75$	Medium	111	68.09 %
$80.75 < X$	High	52	31.91 %
Total		163	100 %

Based on the values in Table II, it can be seen that most employees of the PT X plantation companies which are classified as medium level of employee engagement are 111 employees (68.09%). The rest are employees who are high level of employee engagement is 52 people (31.91%) and no employees are classified as low level of employee engagement.

Employees who generally have a moderate level of engagement need more attention because it is possible to go down, especially in conditions that they deem less profitable. Marciano (2010) says that employees with a moderate level of engagement tend to complain and have the desire to leave the company when they are faced with a difficult situation. This condition is related to the situation of companies that until now still continue to make changes which certainly make employees feel difficult to deal with.

Meanwhile, if the characteristics of these employees are engaged, they will be eager to spend energy in working and willing to work beyond self-limits (Cataldo, 2011). From the results of a study conducted by Marciano (2010) regarding the engagement of employees expressed the behaviors shown by bound employees, one of which was to support and encourage group members. Then interpersonal relationships that support and help each other between employees will increase the level of engagement from employees (Vazirani, 2007).

Workers who have a high level of engagement will have a high emotional attachment to the organization, so that it will have an effect on completing work and tend to have a satisfactory quality of work (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Workers who are engaged will be motivated to increase their productivity, willing to accept challenges and feel their work gives meaning to themselves. This will have a positive impact on the performance of workers, as well as for organizational productivity and growth. Then it can be said that engagement can provide changes for both individuals, teams and organizations (Margaretha & Saragih, 2008).

While the characteristics of employees who are not engaged according to Cataldo (2011) are looking at work as a

condition to get a salary, coming and going home to work on time, always using opportunities for holidays, working improperly according to standard operating procedure (SOP), not voluntarily willing to carry out tasks outside the main task, and lack of enthusiasm in finding new ideas for work. Employee engagement not only makes employees contribute more, but also makes them have higher loyalty, thereby reducing the desire to leave the company voluntarily (Macey & Schneider, 2008). Then Saks (2006) states that employees who have an engage to the company will commit emotionally and intellectually to the company and will give their best effort beyond what is targeted in a job.

Based on these results, it can also be explained by looking at the characteristics of the research subject, in which 77.31% of the research subjects belong to the category of early adulthood. According to Hurlock (1993) early adulthood is a stage of development where a person has more severe responsibilities because at this stage individuals are in the phase of building family life, thinking about economic and future independence.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, employees of the PT X plantation companies are categorized as having medium level of employee engagement. Thus, the employees of the PT X plantation companies are generally need more attention because there is a possibility of engagement be going down, especially in conditions that they consider less profitable. This research implies that the organization can find out how far the employee engagement to their employees, so it can be used as a reference for the organization to create a human resource development strategy related to employee engagement results in this study. This research also can be an input for PT X plantation companies to enhance the social interaction and togetherness that exists in the director's office through activities such as gatherings.

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